

From Pollution to Solution: Evaluating ETP Effectiveness and Future Sustainability in the Textile Industry

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Bangladesh's textile sector strongly supports the economy but is a major polluter; water contamination from heavy chemical and dye use is a serious concern. Producing 1 kg of textile consumes approximately 80 to 200 litres of water, which is then contaminated with trace metals (Cu, Zn, As, Cr) and dyes, threatening aquatic life and human health. This study evaluates a textile factory's Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) over 15 days in March 2025. Daily inlet and outlet measurements of pH, T.D.S., D.O., and temperature were analysed to assess treatment effectiveness. Results show markedly improved water quality with lower pH and TDS, higher D.O., and a moderate temperature decrease. The ETP employs hydrochloric acid, polyelectrolyte, PAC, decoloring agents, and other chemical, physicochemical, and biological processes. Total cost depends on treated volume, flow rate, chemical consumption, and related expenses. Renewable energy is discussed for its potential to reduce pollution and costs, but is not yet used. To further enhance efficiency and sustainability, advanced oxidation processes such as TiO₂ with UV or H₂O₂ with UV should be considered. Overall, the findings underscore the critical role of ETPs in mitigating textile effluent impacts and offer practical avenues for improvement.

1. Introduction

The textile industry is crucial to Bangladesh's GDP and employment. The Ready-Made Garment (RMG) sector accounts for nearly 80% of Bangladesh's exports and 12% of its GDP, making it the largest manufacturing sector with 4.4 million people (Nazrul et al., 2023). Approximately 3,500 operational RMG industries, according to recent estimates (Practice et al., 2023), rely heavily on water and energy in their production processes, which include scoring, bleaching, dyeing, printing, and finishing, leading to the generation of highly contaminated and toxic wastewater. The typical groundwater usage for textile processing in Bangladesh is reported to be 164 litres per kg, exacerbating local water scarcity (Uddin et al., 2023). In 2015, more than 1700 textile dyeing mills utilized approximately 1,500 billion liters of groundwater, which was later released as treated effluent into the environment, intensifying water pollution and groundwater depletion (Ashraf, 2015). Furthermore, the sector produces extensive wastewater, averaging 119 liters per kg of textile processed (Uddin et al., 2023). The effluent dumped into nearby canals and rivers contains

harmful dyes, trace metals (Cd, Cu, Zn, Pb, and Cr), and chemicals that harm agriculture and aquatic ecosystems. Copper concentrations under 1.0 mg/L threaten aquatic plants, and amounts nearing this threshold could adversely affect fish (Sani, 2022). Ammonia, in free (un-ionized) concentrations of 10-50 µg/L or greater cause concerns to fish, while sulphides in the effluent can worsen regional air quality if not sufficiently controlled, threatening vegetation, humans and materials (Yusuf and Sonibare, 2004). Moreover, these contaminants lead to waterborne disorders such as dermatitis, mucous membrane, nasal septum perforation and respiratory tract irritation (Mahfuza et al., 2009). The effluent from this industry frequently demonstrates high levels of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), leading to significant water pollution (Chaurasia et al., 2023; Dhameliya and Ambasana, 2023). To alleviate these problems, Effluent Treatment Plants (ETPs) are essential in the textile industry, addressing the significant environmental challenges that come with wastewater. ETPs use chemical, biological, and physicochemical techniques. Chemical treatments, including precipitation and adsorption, are effective but frequently result in secondary contamination due to sludge production

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(Maria Jonstrup, 2011; Saxena et al., 2020). Conversely, biological treatments employing microorganisms such as fungi, bacteria and algae provide an environmentally friendly solution by degrading harmful dyes (Kishor et al., 2020; Shoaib et al., 2022). Hybrid approaches, including membrane bioreactors and photocatalysis, integrate biological and physicochemical processes to improve treatment efficiency, minimize chemical consumption, and decrease operational expenses (Maria Jonstrup, 2011; Zeeshan et al., 2022). Despite the extensive implementation of ETPs, their efficacy exhibits significant variation, with removal efficiency for pollutants such as microfibers fluctuating between 23.52% to 82.19% (Haque et al., 2024). In Madhabdi, ETPs have not sufficiently resolved concerns of heavy metal contamination in soil and water, highlighting persistent environmental challenges (Rahman and Rahman, 2024). The continual contamination results occur because of lack of environmental restrictions and monitoring systems, since numerous factories release untreated or poorly treated water due to weak oversight. The insufficient presence of automated water quality monitoring intensifies the issue, as existing methods frequently do not deliver prompt notifications for irregularities (Gupta et al., 2023). Additionally, limited staff involvement and management support, which are essential for efficient ETP operations, makes ISO 9001:2008 compliance difficult (Hajar, n.d.).

The energy requirements of wastewater treatment facilities are an issue, with consumption varying from 0.5 to 2.0 kWh per m³ of treated water, depending on plant configuration, technology and water quality (Hamawand, 2023). A study of a textile ETP in Tongi demonstrated that biological treatment procedures are essential for energy efficiency (Hasan et al., 2022). The dependence on energy-intensive methods and expensive imported chemicals multiplies treatment costs, triggering smaller factories to evade compliance with treatment rules (Khandaker et al., 2020). The implementation of solar energy offers a viable solution to this problem. An entirely intuitionistic fuzzy model showed the capability of solar energy to lower expenses and decrease energy wastage in the textile production (Kousar et al., 2022). Along with that, high-temperature solar panels in textile factories have shown substantial thermal energy savings, consistent with global initiatives to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions (Carnevale et al., 2011).

Advanced Oxidation Process (AOPs) have further enhanced wastewater treatment effectiveness, with TiO₂ employed alongside UV radiation of H₂O₂ exhibiting notable outcomes. The combined application of Ce-TiO₂ nanocatalysts with sonophotocatalysis and H₂O₂ resulted in an impressive Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) reduction of 84.75%, surpassing the efficacy of each method independently (Dey et al., 2023). Likewise, UV-assisted photocatalytic degradation of azo dyes resulted in full mineralization and significant COD reduction, highlighting the critical roles of catalyst concentration and H₂O₂ addition (Manjusha Kulkarni, 2023). The UV/H₂O₂ pretreatment method improves the success rate of TiO₂/PVDF membranes, with a COD removal efficiency of 63.64% in continuous operations (Vatanpour et al., 2022). Thus, the purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of the ETP at Far East Knitting & Dyeing Ind. Ltd. (FEKDIL), East Chandra, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

2. Methodology

The ETP comprises multiple treatment phases, as represented in Fig. 1a, with comprehensive details regarding the volume and function of each tank presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The wastewater samples for this study were collected over a period of 15 days from the inlet, which comprises a blend of chemical agents required for scouring, bleaching, dyeing, printing, washing and finishing, and as well as from the outlet of the ETP. On the other hand, collecting data took place during four specific time intervals daily: 10 AM, 12 PM, 3PM and 5 PM. A 1000 mL Imhoff cone was taken from the FEKDIL ETP lab to collect wastewater from the inlet and outlet drain (**Error! Reference source not found.** 1b) for preliminary settling. In this ETP, assessed crucial factors such as Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), pH and temperature.

Table 1 Summary of tank volumes and functions in the ETP process.

Stage	Tank Name	Volume (m ³)	Function
Initial Collection	ECT (Effluent Collection Tank)	94	Collects effluent before treatment
Equalization	EQT (Equalization Tank)	1109	Balances flow variations

Primary Flocculation	PFT (Primary Flocculation Tank)	35	Initial flocculation
Primary Sedimentation	PIPS (Primary Include Plate Settler)	150	Solid particle settling
pH Correction	pH CT (pH Correction Tank)	36	pH adjustment (HCl added)
Biological Treatment (D.O Check)	SBR-1 & SBR-2 (Sequencing Batch Reactor)	1018.5	Bacteria treatment to control DO levels
Intermediate Buffering	IT (Intermediate Tank)	375	Holding tank before further treatment
Tertiary Flocculation	TFT (Tertiary Flocculation Tank)	35	Chemical flocculation (PAC, decoloring agent)
Sludge Management	SHT (Sludge Holding Tank)	220	Sludge of tertiary solids
Final Sedimentation	TIPS (Tertiary Inclined Plate Settler)	150	Settling of tertiary solids
Ozone Treatment	OCT (Ozone Contact Tank)	82	Final ozone treatment
Outlet	Not specified	Not specified	Discharge of treated water.

Fig. 1 a) Flowchart of the ETP process. b) Imhoff cones.

2.1 Chemical treatment cost analysis

The chemical treatment cost analysis was conducted based on post-treatment data collected from the effluent treatment plant. The study focused on the actual quantities and costs of chemicals used during the treatment process, including Hydrochloric Acid (HCl), Poly Aluminum Chloride (PAC), Decoloring Agent, Poly-Electrolyte, Diammonium Phosphate (DAP), and Urea. These data were obtained from the factory's daily chemical usage records and expense logs. The information reflects the direct chemical cost incurred per treatment cycle and was used to calculate the average treatment cost per cubic meter of wastewater.

2.2 Sample and data collection

Each sample was collected in a 500 mL beaker, which was rinsed and cleaned with distilled water to avert contamination, from the Imhoff cone. Initially, the temperature was quickly measured by immersing a glass thermometer for about 90 seconds. Subsequently, the USEPA Electrode Method was employed to ascertain pH using the HQ40D Multimeter, from which the pH value was recorded. The testing procedure for Dissolved Oxygen (DO) was also conducted with the HQ40D Multimeter. Finally, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) were measured directly with the same multimeter, expressed in mg/L. The study also evaluated the chemicals cost-effectiveness and examined the amount of chemicals used in the treatment process.

3. Results and discussion

Since several textile production facilities share this ETP, there was a great chance that wastewater quality would vary time to time. Temperature, TDS, DO and pH were the main water quality metrics assessed. A summary of the average values for each water quality metric over the course of 15 days, arranged by time to time intervals, is shown in **Table 2**. For each parameter measured at the inlet and outlet flow, the average values are displayed.

Table 2 Average water quality parameters over 15 days.

Parameter	Time Interval	Inlet Average (15 days)	Outlet Average (15 days)	Percent Change (%)	Standard Values
pH	10 AM	7.70	6.97	Reduction 9.48	pH= 6-9 TDS= 2100 mg/L Temp.= Not more than 5°C of water body. DO= 4.5-8 mg/L
	12 PM	8.17	7.00	Reduction 14.32	
	3 PM	8.60	7.14	Reduction 16.97	
	5 PM	8.87	6.95	Reduction 21.64	
TDS (mg/L)	10 AM	804.47	1048.80	Increase 30.37	pH= 6-9 TDS= 2100 mg/L Temp.= Not more than 5°C of water body. DO= 4.5-8 mg/L
	12 PM	1035.40	1057.54	Increase 2.13	
	3 PM	1327.27	1065.00	Reduction 19.76	
	5 PM	1378.40	1076.20	Reduction 21.92	
DO (mg/L)	10 AM	1.87	5.65	Increase 202.13	pH= 6-9 TDS= 2100 mg/L Temp.= Not more than 5°C of water body. DO= 4.5-8 mg/L
	12 PM	1.82	5.62	Increase 208.79	
	3 PM	1.84	5.64	Increase 206.52	
	5 PM	1.82	5.75	Increase 215.93	
Temperature (°C)	10 AM	32.28	30.57	Reduction 5.29	pH= 6-9 TDS= 2100 mg/L Temp.= Not more than 5°C of water body. DO= 4.5-8 mg/L
	12 PM	33.83	30.92	Reduction 8.60	
	3 PM	34.65	31.20	Reduction 9.95	
	5 PM	35.40	31.42	Reduction 11.24	

3.1 pH results

The inlet mean value range is 7.65 ± 0.76 to 9.17 ± 0.76 , whereas the outlet mean value range is 6.64 ± 0.37 to 7.38 ± 0.37 , in comparison to the DoE norm of 6 to 9, as shown in the Fig. 2, demonstrates that the pH of the inlet wastewater is exceedingly high due to its very alkaline nature. The various chemical agents utilized in the procedures are responsible for the high alkalinity of the wastewater. This research use HCl to adjust the pH, achieving a neutral level that is optimal for biological treatment. The highest pH value in the inlet was recorded as 10 on days 12 and 15, whereas the lowest value was 7, which occurred most frequently during the 15-day period. The greatest outlet value was recorded as 7.5, while the lowest value was 6.5; both values were frequently documented. The percentage of reduction changed from 9.48 to 21.64, which shows that adding HCl to the pH Correction Tank worked to make the solution more acidic.

Fig. 2 Inlet and Outlet pH with time and day.

3.2 TDS results

The mean value range of the inlet is from 804.47 ± 243.62 to 1378.47 ± 357.19 , whereas the mean value range for the outlet is from 1048.80 ± 138.26 to 1076.20 ± 174.18 , against the DoE standard of 2100 mg/l. The **Error! Reference source not found.** showed that the maximum inlet value was 2116 mg/L at 5 PM on day 14, while the minimum was 336 mg/L at 10 AM on day 1. Both the greatest and smallest value were seen at 5 PM, measuring 1388 mg/L on day 15 and 733 mg/L on day 1, respectively. This pattern becomes apparent in **Error! Reference source not found.**, which provides a clear overview of the removal efficacy. Over the duration of 15 days and four periods of data analysis, the TDS remains below the accepted level of the DoE standard. The ECR-2023 scale confirmed the value.

Fig. 3 Inlet and Outlet TDS with time and day.

3.3 DO results

The inlet DO exhibits a mean value range of 1.68 ± 0.17 to 2.02 ± 0.17 , while the outlet DO shows a mean value range of 5.48 ± 0.19 to 5.87 ± 0.19 . These values are assessed in relation to the DoE standard of 4.5 to 8 mg/L, as depicted in the Fig. 4. The data presented in the figure indicates that the highest DO value of wastewater at the inlet was measured at 2.6 mg/L at 5 PM on day 2, while the lowest recorded value was 1.4 mg/L on multiple days. The maximum recorded value in the outlet was 6.9 mg/L on day 15, while the lowest value was 4.5 mg/L at 10 AM on day 9. After a thorough examination of the data collected over 15 days, it can be concluded that the DO value was maintained within the acceptable limits set by the DoE standard.

Fig. 4 Inlet and Outlet DO with time and day.

3.4 Temperature Results

This study reported a maximum average inlet temperature of 36.4°C on day 13, with a low temperature of 30.9°C on day 12, as illustrated in Fig. 5. On the other hand, the maximum average temperature at the exit was recorded at 32.1°C on day 8, with a minimum temperature of 29.9°C on day 9. During the 15-day data analysis, the measured temperature drop percentages ranged from $3.8\% \pm 4.44\%$ to $12.68\% \pm$

4.44%, indicating effective temperature regulation throughout the treatment period.

Fig. 5 Inlet and Outlet average temperature.

3.5 Chemical treatment cost analysis

The analysis of daily chemical usage revealed that the Decoloring Agent was the most expensive component in the treatment process, accounting for the highest daily cost due to its high unit price. Poly Aluminum Chloride (PAC) followed, contributing significantly to overall expenses due to its relatively high consumption. In contrast, chemicals such as Hydrochloric Acid (HCl), Urea, DAP, and Poly-Electrolyte had comparatively lower costs, either due to lower pricing or limited usage. These findings indicate that a few specific chemicals dominate the operational costs, suggesting potential targets for cost-reduction strategies. The amounts of chemicals varied daily based on the quality of the incoming effluent demonstrated Table 3.

Table 3 Average chemical consumption and cost at FEKDIL.

Chemical	Average Quantity (kg/day)	Price (tk/kg)	Average Cost (tk/day)
PAC	121.66	58	7056.28
Decoloring Agent	83.57	155	12953.35
HCl	217.80	6.10	1328.58
Poly-Electrolyte	0.84	280	235.2
Urea	12.13	27	327.51
Dap	6	20.40	122.4

4. Sustainability consideration

Chemical treatment reduced contaminants significantly, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Besides assessing existing performance, the study suggests using solar energy to offset ETP electricity usage, which could reduce operational costs and make water treatment more sustainable. Bangladesh has significant solar energy potential because of its geographical location. Due to the limited availability of land, rooftop solar is a feasible method for augmenting solar power output in the textile sector. In conformity with global trends, the cost per unit of electricity produced by rooftop solar in Bangladesh has been reduced to Tk 5.5–6.5 per kilowatt hour, affected by solar insolation, investment approach, and equipment utilization. Between 2010 and 2018, the global weighted average cost of electricity from all commercially available renewable energy technologies declined, with solar photovoltaic technology experiencing the most substantial percentage decrease, which is 77. The price of grid power for industrial users presently varies between Tk 7.25 and Tk 10.19 per unit, depending on the usage time and voltage level. Considering the prevailing cost of grid In March 2024, FEKDIL's power rate was Tk 7.48 per unit, with the factory's average consumption amounting to 327,338.13 units. Far East Spinning Industries Ltd. (FESIL), located in the Habiganj district, has installed a solar photovoltaic system with a capacity of 1.1 MWp and AC output of 1 MW, employing available ground spaces and rooftops. FESIL saved Tk 6.337 million in electricity costs over an eight-month period from November 2018 to June 2019 (The financial express, 2019). Consequently, if the industry can replace up to 50% of its energy with solar power, operational costs and carbon emissions will decrease. This study recommends the implementation of solar energy to reduce

ETP operational costs, improve the sustainability of water treatment, and minimize CO₂ emissions.

5. Conclusion

The evaluation of the ETP at FEKDIL demonstrates its effectiveness in improving key water quality parameters, ensuring compliance with the Environmental Conservation Rules (ECR) 1997. The ETP successfully neutralized the highly alkaline inlet pH, reducing it to an outlet pH within the DoE standard of 6-9, representing a significant reduction. TDS at the inlet were managed to an outlet well below the DoE limit of 2100 mg/L. Crucially, the DO levels dramatically improved, indicating effective biological treatment. Furthermore, the outlet temperature was reduced, meeting acceptable limits.

Despite these successes, challenges persist, particularly concerning TDS levels and operational costs, with daily chemical expenses being substantial. To enhance sustainability and address these challenges, the adoption of renewable energy sources is highly recommended. Solar energy, for instance, offers a cost-effective alternative to grid electricity. Implementing advanced oxidation techniques, which show promise in achieving high COD reduction, should also be explored for improved efficiency. Continuous monitoring and strict compliance with environmental regulations are essential for long-term sustainability.

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Conflict-of-Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Author Contribution

Sayam: conceived and designed the study; conducted all experiments; acquired, curated, and analyzed the data; developed the methodology; prepared figures; wrote the manuscript; and approved the final version.

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